

PHILOSOPHY

POSTMODERN ANTHROPOLOGY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE CONTEMPORARY RELATIONAL CRISIS

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Abstract

The article examines the problem of the crisis of relations, which is manifested in the apparent increase in violence around the world, from the point of view of the conceptual heritage of philosophical anthropology, in particular, the psychoanalytic theory of personality development and the poststructuralist criticism.

As we believe, these approaches allow us to formulate the above problem exactly in philosophical terms, i.e., in the terms of discovering the correlation between human involvement into the postindustrial production system and poststructuralist teaching about libidinal economy. For, according to poststructuralist vision, it is libidinal economy that enables us to suppress some aggressive strives by absorbing energy, substituting the gratification of primitive urges for an advanced system of the social awards.

Additionally, this paper testifies that when we are within the framework of psychoanalytic and postmodern anthropology, we can conclude: the answer to the question, where the huge amount of human destructive energy goes, which is not investing in production relations, lies in the sphere of interpersonal relationships.

Put it differently, we are forced to admit that the contemporary social system, namely its institutional structure, is faced with essential difficulties in the matter of regulating interpersonal relationships, since it appears to be powerless against the phenomenon of malignant violence.

Keywords: aggressiveness, abusive practices, destructive libido, malignant violence, libidinal economy, postmodern anthropology, transgressive behavior.

Main text of the article. It is known that by the end of 20th century, an interesting phenomenon in contemporary philosophical thought emerged, which identified itself as “philosophy of the surface”. This trend is better known to be postmodern philosophy, which, as we believe, is of particular interest, precisely due to its specific anthropology. What exactly do we have in mind when we talk about a specific anthropology within the framework of postmodern philosophy?

Firstly, it refers to a large role of some findings in the development of postmodern knowledge about humans, namely, the psychoanalytic theory of individuals and key ideas by Fredrix Nietzsche regarding the relativity of personality mental structure. Secondly, the postmodern theory of human nature appeared to be the most critical of all that had ever existed.

The first assumption is the effect of evident striving to elucidate the fundamental structure of the human unconscious on the part of some postmodernists that completely corresponds to the major task of theoretical psychoanalysis. Furthermore, most of them were convinced of the decisive influence of the so-called *destructive libido* on the development of both the mental type of personality and the fundamental social institutions.

A vivid example of the fusion of postmodernism and psychoanalysis can be found in the so-called strategy of “schizo-analysis”, developed by prominent representatives of the poststructuralist trend. But, despite

of general concern with the conceptualizing and structuring of unconscious (the theory of “Schizoid Subject”), leading post-structuralist philosophers were no less engaged in the issue of superfluous violence or put it in postmodern term, in the issue of transgressive experience.

Furthermore, most of them were convinced of the validity of an idea on prime cruelty of humans, rather than having some doubts about this, *treating cruelty as a basic passion of humanity, an original (barbaric) way of extraction of the surplus value as well*, especially when alternative sources of gratification are basically impossible. There is talking, primarily, about the specific surplus value, deriving from human suffering or as Nietzsche claimed: “To see suffering does you good, to make suffering better still – that is a hard proposition... to which, by the way, even the apes might subscribe” [3, 42-43]. For this reason, Deleuze, for example, classified humanism as “a stranger piety”, since, presumably, humanism, like the experience of moral feelings as such, is incapable of giving pleasure to the same extent as the pleasure in destruction, atrocity, ferocity towards the innocent, etc.

The weakness of transcendental arguments. In this regard, *postmodern anthropologies draw special attention to the possible elucidation of the genesis of Moral Subject, predicated on a rather founded criticism of transcendental ethic* as a philosophical teaching on the unconditional nature of the sense of duty, that is,

of such a structure that forces us to comply with the moral imperatives.

As far as the emergence of human morality is concerned, Nietzsche, for example, insisted on the decisive function of fear. In other words, it was this feeling that he considered to be the fundamental affective basis for designing the sense of duty.

This perspective on moral genesis has found additional substantiation in psychoanalysis, namely in the theory of Oedipus complex, which can be regarded as a kid's fear of being punished by his parents (that is the reason why there is always a latent hatred toward them), coexisting with a strong kid's attachment.

To put it differently, Freud believed that the further transformation of the Oedipus construct into a sense of duty was carried out both because of the fear of punishment and because of the fear of losing parental love. Thus, even though Freud focused his attention on attachment (affective values), in the matter of the moral development of the individual, he trusted more and relied on the feeling of fear.

But it is Kierkegaard who is known to be the first to pose the issue of the complexity of the correlation between affection and *the sense of duty*, emphasizing the impact of a certain constellation of human feelings, which contributes to the development of moral and religious consciousness: "The fortunate chance in life is that the two correspond, that my wish is my duty and *vice versa*, and the task of most men in life is precisely to remain within their duty and by their enthusiasm to transform it into their wish" [2,154]. But this perspective on the nature of very moral duty remains obscure, probably due to his specific concern with religious experience ("an absolute duty toward God"), rather than morality, which, as well-known, he was inclined to contrast with faith. For instance, in some places, Kierkegaard hesitates between *fear* ("constant tension" and trembling or terror) towards the Lord and *affection* in terms of the possible reason for the sense of duty. But in other ones, when reasoning about love itself, he writes about some *duty to love*, in relation to that the issue of grasping the nature of the above feelings becomes increasingly complex. For, apparently, the *duty to love* is merely a "concept", which is no less transcendental than Kant's "categorical imperative".

In contrast to the above transcendentalism, representatives of poststructuralist's discourse offer an extremely "gloomy" anthropology, where we can feel no less extreme impact of Nietzschean ideas. Similar to Nietzsche, they continue to expose the ethical in a person with the help of analyzing and referring to various technologies for designing a socially useful Subject, emphasizing their efficiency. Along with that, they mostly support his doctrine about humans as animals, captivated by their instincts and desires, namely by the social instincts of power and accumulation.

In addition, the developers of postmodern anthropology are questioning the universal nature of *empathy*, rejecting the theory of the original inability of humanity to libidinal aggressiveness, offered, for example, by Wilhelm Reich. According to them, the human mental structure is subject to historical transformation in terms of its tendency both towards evolution and involution,

therefore the discussion about human nature seems to be unfounded. What do they mean?

At first glance, according to postmodernists every human individual is the effect of socialization, realized mostly because of a strong feeling of fear, primarily in terms of natural fear (self-preservative instinct). They often refer to both the fear of punishment established by the community and the social fear of losing social rank, esteem, respectability etc. If the repressive institutions, and along with them, the positive sanctions do not work, the "designing" of "docile Subjects" (Michle Foucault) in society seems problematic, therefore the increase of dangerous tendencies can be observed.

But postmodern thinkers also emphasize that the above social fear, as well as so-called *empathy* (compassion) are very relative tendencies that have an individual history. In other words, one person tends to be compassionate, another, *vice versa*, shows incredible atrocity. It is not a coincidence, in contemporary humanitarian studies much attention is paid to such "persons" as psychopaths, sociopaths and schizoids.

The aforementioned types of personality are characterized by *affective emasculation* in terms of their inclination to devalue their surroundings. They are completely indifferent to attachment and constructive relationships, aimed at establishing permanent social connections. We can say that they do not care less about any attachments on the part of others, "miserable whimpering about not being loved and understood" [1, 268], since they are incapable of experiencing any affection for people. That is the reason why, Parsons' "relational awards" are just words for them.

In addition, in many contemporary theories one can observe an unanimously shared belief in the decisive influence of institutions on personality development. The major issue of most of them is related to grasping to what extent the institutional mechanisms can exercise control over the human "passions", and what exactly they are? *In other words, to what extent is the desire for violence subject to the civilizational "bridling"?*

It is hardly possible to contest the postmodern assertion about the mediation of the civilizing process by elaboration of various mechanisms to struggle with destructive impulses, as well as the major role of "the bloody festival of punishment" (Michle Foucault) in the implementation of the social control over people. Perhaps the outstanding German sociologist, namely Norbert Elias was quite right, when he stated concerning evolution of the part of humanity in the direction of increasing the control over some feelings, emotions and passions. But, as for the human desire for "bloody spectacles", everything is not so simple.

2. "People of abuse" in the postmodern era. Indeed, in so-called advanced societies, the primitive ritual cruelty or bloody atrocity, the various barbarous institutional practices, have long lost their lawfully. In this context, it is very often said about the relative humanization of social relations, including the penitentiary system of many countries, primarily due to the development of industrial and financial capitalism (we can clearly refer to such prominent authors as the above Michle Foucault, Norbert Elias, Deni de Rougemont, etc.).

The fact remains that until societies had reached a high degree of material values development, they were hardly concerned with the extreme cruelty of their mores. Nevertheless, the same Elias rightly emphasized that even in the ancient period of human civilization, the so-called “noble beasts of prey” (Nietzsche) mutilated and killed with a particular cruelty those who could not pay off.

The idea of the extreme impact of industrial capitalism on the entire Western civilization, development of which allowed, so to speak, to “softening” essentially the sanctions by offering an alternative incentive facilities in the form of the system of awards for labor, the social esteems, approvals, etc., that is a “libidinal economy”, seems to be entirely acceptable. And yet the numerous daily practices of violence in the context of these societies (harassment, bullying, abuse, etc.), that is, current relational crisis testifies that Elias's *saying about the opportunity of replacing the desire for violence with the desire for accumulation, for example, may encounter strong libidinal resistance*. For where do the variety of abusive practices come from, namely, physical or sexual abuse, violent or threatening behavior, controlling or coercive behavior, economic, psychological, emotional abuse, etc.?

It is not a coincidence that most of mentioned above cases belong to domestic violence, that is, to the practices of abuse in intimate relations, since apparently, the dependence of potential victims, including emotional one is frequently the most common reason for abusive behavior on the part of abuser (especially, when he holds sway).

Even if we admit the validity of so-called sublimation, we must conceive that it is never excessive in terms of that even with the most noble impulses there is always a shadow of disappointment or dissatisfaction with life, which can scarcely be dispelled in a constructive way.

Furthermore, the experience of *transgressive behavior* in relatively prosperous societies does not point in favor of the above-mentioned noble impulses. Presumably, violence in relationships under conditions of advanced societies can be classified as the most primitive way of extracting the ‘surplus value’ on the part of human majority, the kind of pleasure from the displeasure or suffering of those who are hurt. Annual increase of violence, related, for instance, to notorious domestic abuse, in particular, abusive behavior towards children and women testifies in favor of the above presupposition.

Take, for example, child abuse, which is known to be a more common experience in America and around the world. According to statistics for 2022 “*1 billion children globally are estimated to experience sexual violence*”. In general, the most widespread practices of violence towards children are related to four basic types of abuse: these are physical, sexual, emotional and neglect. But the fact remains that *most abusive cases toward children are victimized by a parent or legal guardian (76-77%), that is, they are closely associated with domestic violence* [5].

As for abusive relationships in German families, for example, it is known that in recent times “the num-

ber of victims of domestic violence has increased significantly over the past five years, reaching 256,276 in 2023 (2019: 214,481; an increase of 19.5%). In 2023, victims of intimate partner violence accounted for 65.5% (167,865 victims) of all domestic violence cases, while 34.5% (88,411 victims) were attributed to intra-familial violence. (BKA, Domestic Violence Situation Report 2023, page 7). The current crime statistics analysis on intimate partner violence by the Federal Criminal Police Office (BKA, 2024) shows that a total of 167.865 people were victims of intimate partner violence in 2023. This is an increase of 9.1% compared to 2022. 132.966 (79,2%) victims were female and 34.899 (20,8%) male” [4].

Numerous manifestations of abusive practices only confirm the validity of postmodern assertion about its libidinal basis, that is, violence can become only one source of gratification for many people. Put it differently, striving for violence, supposedly, is mediated by strong affective impulses. When the abuser loses the opportunity for such perverted pleasure, he often resorts to an extreme form of destructiveness: “the risk of serious assault and death is highest for a woman after she leaves an abusive relationship. According to the Femicide Census, 38% of women killed by their ex-partner from 2009 to 2018 were killed within the first month of separation and 89% in the first year” [4].

That is the reason why for today the discussion in contemporary anthropology is more related to the matter of “malignant aggression” (Erich Fromm), rather than, what is a “primary” or, conversely, a “secondary” put it in philosophical terms in arising of human civilization – an economic function of exchange (Claude Levi-Strauss, J. Baudrillard) or an unavoidable institutional repression (Z. Freud, F. Nietzsche, F. Guattari).

Presumably, the libidinal destructive urge of humans as well as their instinctive feeling of fear, is unlikely subject to cultural correction. When such “drives” capture whole groups or masses of human individuals, they can turn into huge power with very fatal consequences. However, it is these human impulses that invest into the system of social relations, allowing them to exist and reproduce: “Even the most repressive and the most deadly forms of social reproduction are produced by desire within organization that is consequence of such production under various conditions...” [1, 38].

Postmodernists, who are mostly poststructuralists, point to the process of “blurring” of social roles (behavioral patterns), which takes place under conditions of postmodern society that is reflected in their grasping of the “libidinal economy”. According to them, currently neither desire for work, that is Weber’s “industriousness” or Marcuse’s “libidinal labor”, nor striving for recognition and status esteem, as Parsons believed, can form the motivation for work anymore. If we refer to the present production system, its libidinal basis is, largely, to the desire for “flows” and notorious “surplus value”, profits. That is the reason why the current “sticker” (Michele Foucault) of individuals to work is carried out directly, released for the most part from any discipline and self-constraint.

It is obvious, the total weakness of the institutional system of social roles and behavioral standards in the

so-called advanced societies has led to the problem of increasing destructive tendencies that concerns every “collective”, starting with family and ending with production. It is this proposition that laid the basis of post-modern criticism of structuralism in terms of denying the overestimation of the influence of ethical codes on social integration.

Conclusion. So, instincts and other impulses of humankind are the most widespread topics for post-modern anthropological studies throughout the 20th century, there is an increasing concern about their classification, substantiation of their libidinal basis. Much attention is paid to the correlation between very hatred and the desire for violence with an emphasis on the essential difference between them in the sense that the latter does not always originate from hatred. Nevertheless, it does not mean that these passions are not able to combine between themselves, “designing” completely destructive individuals. Along with that, such individuals can be involved, and they are involved in the system of social relations due to the possibility of only partial re-integration of their libido into production activities.

As postmodernists rightly state, destructive impulses are not totally antisocial in terms of the social system being incapable of extracting from them any use or “profit”, rather *vice versa*: destructive tendencies can also perform positive social functions. These are, supposed to be very strong impulses, and along with that, no less intensive productive resource, which can be invested into the established system of relations, based on the notorious “pecking order”, maintaining its existence ostensibly from the inside.

Presumably for this reason, ever Herbert Marcuse, for example, believed in the libidinal basis of both economic and political institutions, since it is these fundamental departments of social life that can turn into objects, which absorb libidinal energy, enabling them to reproduce themselves again and again: the “libidinal

flows” or impulses in the forms of the desire for power or dominance, accumulation, etc. that are more effective mechanisms for operation of the social system, rather than some conventional codes or the system of social recognition.

But it would be wrong to reduce even contemporary societies to a political-economic basis alone, devaluating or overlooking the sphere of personal relationships, which for the majority of “living human individuals” is still relevant to such an extent that it requires a sufficiently high level of moral and mental development. Presumably, this moral development is promoted at the expense of the close interdependence of individuals. For if individuals are not personally attached or concerned with each other, rather conversely, there is only a clash of “two freedoms”, as Sartre claimed, then a dangerous tendency, therefore relational crisis can only intensify, leading humanity to the triumph of violence and self-destruction.

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